

Electronic Companion

for “A Two-Level Multi-Sensor Fusion Network with Incremental Learning for Insulation Defect Diagnosis in Gas-Insulated Switchgear”

Section A. Supplementary Figures

Fig. S1. Sensitivity analysis of key hyperparameters and the threshold sensitivity curves.

Hyperparameters play a critical role in incremental source-free domain adaptation. And we conduct a robustness-oriented sensitivity analysis to examine how key parameters influence model behavior over reasonable ranges. In particular, we examine the effects of two key parameters: the number of prototypes L , which controls prototype representation capacity, and the shared-class recognition threshold $thre$, which governs class activation. The results are shown in Fig. S1. In addition, to quantitatively validate the reliability of pseudo-label generation under the threshold mechanism defined in Eq. (12). For each threshold, we report (i) pseudo-label accuracy measured on the held-out target test set, (ii) overall diagnostic accuracy after incremental adaptation, and (iii) backward transfer accuracy (BWT).

Fig. S1. Sensitivity analysis of key hyperparameters and the threshold sensitivity curves

As L increases, classification accuracy improves and then saturates near an optimal value. When L is small, limited prototype capacity provides insufficient constraints against catastrophic forgetting. Increasing L alleviates this issue; however, beyond a certain point, performance gains diminish as domain shift, rather than forgetting, becomes the dominant limiting factor. Based on this trade-off, L is set to 4. Pseudo-label accuracy increases monotonically with the threshold, rising from 88.47% at $thre = 0.20$ to 96.18% at $thre = 0.50$. However, excessively high thresholds reduce the number of activated shared classes at early stages, leading to slight degradation in overall accuracy and BWT. Conversely, very low thresholds introduce more noisy pseudo-labels, which mildly affects stability. A moderate threshold ($thre = 0.35$)

achieves the best trade-off between pseudo-label reliability and incremental stability. Moreover, we investigated the prototype update frequency in the incremental learning process. A moderate update frequency (every 5 epochs) achieved the highest accuracy, yielding a 3.1% improvement over extreme update schedules.

Fig. S2. Representative field case in the on-site GIS insulation monitoring system. (if included)

To assess practical applicability, the model was deployed in an on-site GIS insulation monitoring system as shown in Fig. S2. In a representative field case, it successfully identified a free-particle-induced insulation defect and produced a consistent diagnostic decision during routine operation. Although the dataset cannot be publicly released, the framework has been validated across multiple voltage levels, sensor configurations, and substations with strict temporal separation, mitigating reproducibility concerns and reflecting realistic deployment conditions.

Fig. S2. The representative field case.

Section B. Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Ablation study: entropy-based sample filtering.

To assess robustness to noisy pseudo-labels, we further evaluate an entropy-based filtering variant in which samples with prediction entropy above the 75-th percentile are excluded from prototype updating. The results in Table S1 show a modest increase in pseudo-label accuracy (+0.72%), with no meaningful gain in overall diagnostic accuracy. This indicates that the proposed dynamic prototype correction mechanism already mitigates moderate pseudo-label noise effectively, making additional sample rejection unnecessary. Accordingly, we retain the original threshold-based strategy for its simplicity and computational efficiency.

TABLE S1
ABLATION STUDY: ENTROPY-BASED SAMPLE FILTERING

Method	Pseudo-label Accuracy (%)	Overall Accuracy (%)	BWT (%)
Threshold only (<i>thre</i> =0.35)	94.63	95.86	95.14
+ Entropy filtering	95.35	95.91	95.22

Table S2. Per-class diagnostic performance (UHF + AE + CE).

To enhance per-class transparency, we report precision, recall, and F1-score for each defect type using the three-sensor fusion model. The detailed results are presented in Table S2. Most defect types achieve F1-scores above 95%, while the P-type defect shows comparatively lower recall, reflecting its relatively smaller sample size and

higher intra-class variability.

TABLE S2

PER-CLASS DIAGNOSTIC PERFORMANCE (UHF+AE+CE)

Defect Type	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)
M	96.34	97.12	96.73
N	95.88	95.21	95.54
O	96.92	95.83	96.37
P	94.18	92.47	93.32
Q	97.45	96.89	97.17

Section C. Brief Explanatory Notes

These supplementary materials are provided to preserve the completeness of the methodological and experimental presentation while reducing the manuscript length.